

Keywords:

#data, #OpenScience, #Ruralareas, #Gnomee, #AthenaRC #ResearchObjects, #EOSCinPractice

Athena RC: Empowering Open Science and Digital Transformation for Rural Communities

Leveraging Gnomee web application and interdisciplinary solutions to drive innovation in Greece

The Project Involved

Athena RC is a research organisation focusing on designing and developing inter-disciplinary solutions for research communities and society. It is one of the main Open Science ambassadors in Greece and supports EOSC through various projects. As partner in the DESIRA Horizon 2020 research project (<https://desira2020.eu/>), Athena RC has designed and developed a set of digital tools to facilitate digitalisation in rural areas and agriculture, and strengthen the impact of Living Labs.

The Research Community

Gnomee is a web knowledge base that contains Digital Solutions which can act as potential Digital Game Changers in rural areas, agriculture, and forestry. Each digital solution is classified under a set of taxonomies useful to farmers, facilitators and researchers willing to identify solutions for these areas for exploitation or further enhancement.

The Challenge

To ensure wide acceptance and exploitation of digital tools from - but not only- the research community, it is important to re-use and exploit common solutions and services with regards to core functionalities and operations and not introduce additional options, compared to existing ones. This approach should be followed from applications that require users to create an account. The challenge, in this specific context, is to eliminate the need for asking users to create yet another account and increase the possibility of exploiting the full potential of your web application.

Panagiota Koltsida

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"EOSC offers an integrated research environment that makes services such as OpenAIRE AAI available and accessible. It serves as the single access point for identifying relevant services that suit a specific context, purpose and/or new service".

EOSC service or tool used

To solve the above challenge, we exploited OpenAIRE's AAI service to offer external authentication through a list of well-known providers, including academic institutions, ORCID, as well as social providers like Google and LinkedIn. Using this service, users can login to our application through their existing accounts and can take advantage of the functionality offered to authenticated users.

OpenAIRE's AAI service offers a standard integration method and can be easily integrated by external web applications.

Useful tips & tricks

The main authentication provider for our web application: Gnomee (<https://www.gnomee.eu>) is OpenAIRE AAI service allowing our potential users to be easily authenticated and become members of our application and exploit it further. Integrating with OpenAIRE AAI is an easy task as it supports OAuth2 and SAML standard protocols.

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Benefits and impact

Gnomee Knowledge Base is a community driven tool and, as such, offers the functionality to be updated with new Digital Solutions by users. To support this feature, users need to login to the application in order to suggest new solutions to become part of Gnomee. This feature has been easily implemented exploiting OpenAIRE's AAI EOSC service as an initial step for authenticating the user without requiring significant effort by the user itself allowing him/her to focus on the information of the new suggested digital solution.

Ensuring that Gnomee is updated with new digital solutions, increases its sustainability and potential impact, and facilitates its continuous exploitation from the targeted users.

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC offers an integrated research environment that makes services as the OpenAIRE AAI available and accessible. It acts as the single point of access for identifying interested services, suitable for a specific context, purpose and/or new service. We will explore EOSC in future in case new functionality is going to be implemented as part of the Gnomee web application.

Limitations and future improvement

OpenAIRE AAI service supports all main authentication providers and as such makes it easy for users to select the provider they wish to use. No limitations at this point.

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